

Organic Pesticides. Part VIII. Synthesis of Halo-aryl Esters of Phosphoric and Thiophosphoric Acids and Certain Related Compounds

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Seven substituted fluorophenols have been condensed with *O,O*-diethyl chlorothiophosphate to give esters of thiophosphoric acid, with phosphorous oxychloride to give phosphoric acid esters, and finally with ethylene chlorohydrin to yield the corresponding ethers. All these compounds are expected to possess insecticidal activity.

Organic phosphorus compounds are well known as insecticides¹. In the recent investigations the authors have attempted to synthesise some compounds containing phosphorus and fluorine which physiologically may not be highly toxic like the above compounds¹, but which may possess insecticidal activity and thus be safer to handle. The first group of compounds may be regarded as analogues of Parathion (I) which is a powerful insecticide but is toxic to man and animals and has anti-cholinesterase activity.

These compounds possessing a halo-aryl group (II) and containing fluorine were prepared by refluxing the sodium salts of the appropriate substituted fluorophenol with *O,O*-diethyl chlorothiophosphate for two hours in dry ethanol and isolated by the method of Fletcher *et al*².

The second group of compounds consists of mono- and diaryl esters of phosphoric acid. Maguire and Shaw³ observed that esters of phosphoric acid exhibited biologically active properties in case of plants with long tap roots. A perusal of the literature shows that whereas numerous aryl hydrogen phosphates have been synthesised as insecticides^{1,4}, very little information is available on fluoro-aryl phosphates. Such esters were therefore prepared by condensing the substituted fluorophenols with phosphorus oxychloride. Attempts to synthesise the tri-esters were not successful.

1. Saunders, "Some Aspects of the Chemistry and Toxic Action of Organic Compounds containing Phosphorus and Fluorine", Cambridge University Press, 1957.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3943.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1479.
4. Koeselapoff, "Organic Phosphorus Compounds"; Jacobsen, *Ber.*, 1875, **8**, 1525.

A useful systemic insecticide should be soluble in plant sap. The solubility is increased by the presence of a hydroxyalkyl group and therefore a related group of compounds has been prepared by condensing the various fluorophenols, used for above compounds, with ethylene chlorohydrin.

Further, in all the above compounds, a carbonyl group has been introduced into two compounds of each group with a view to enhancing the insecticidal properties by increasing lipoid solubility.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Fluoro- and *p*-fluorophenols were prepared respectively from *o*-anisidine and *p*-anisidine by following the method of English *et al*⁵.

4,6-Dibromo-2-fluorophenol was prepared by the method described by Raiford and Lerosen⁶.

2,6-Dibromo- and 2,6-di-iodo-4-fluorophenols were prepared by the method of Hodgson and Nixon⁷.

2-Acetyl-4-fluorophenol was prepared by acetylating *p*-fluorophenol (7g.) in the usual manner to yield *p*-fluorophenyl acetate and by the Fries rearrangement of the acetate; yield 8g. (94.1% of theory), m.p. 57°, b. p. 100°. Buu-Hoï *et al*⁸ report m.p. 57° and b.p. 103-104/13 mm.

2-Propionyl-4-fluorophenol.—*p*-Fluoropropionate (6g.) was prepared from *p*-fluorophenol (6g.) and propionyl chloride (5g.) in the usual manner. By the Fries rearrangement, the ester gave 2-propionyl-4-fluorophenol; yield 5g. (83.3% of theory), b.p. 110°/10 mm. Buu Hoi *et al*.⁸ report b.p. 111-12°.

Thiophosphoryl chloride was prepared by heating phosphorus trichloride with powdered sulphur in presence of white anhydrous aluminium chloride according to Bailar Jr⁹. On distillation a colorless liquid was obtained; b.p. 121-23°, yield 96.8% of theory.

O:O-Diethyl Chlorothiophosphate.—A solution of thiophosphoryl chloride (56.5g.) in dry benzene (150 ml) was gradually added at 10-15° to a stirred solution of sodium ethoxide (from 23g. of sodium in 450 ml of dry ethanol). After filtration, the filtrate was concentrated, and the compound distilled as a colorless liquid under reduced pressure, b.p. 65-70°/5-6mm, yield 40g. (63.3% of theory).

Esters of Thiophosphoric Acid.—A mixture of anhydrous salt of the requisite phenol (1 M), *O:O*-diethyl chlorothiophosphate (1M), and dry ethanol was heated for 2 hours and then cooled to 20°. It was filtered and the filtrate concentrated at the pump. It was heated at the pump at 70°/5mm to expel any excess of the phosphate. The residue was taken in toluene and washed successively with 5% sodium carbonate solution and water; it was dried, the toluene removed, and the compound distilled under reduced pressure. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table I.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 350.

6. *Ibid.*, 1944, **66**, 2086.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1086.

8. *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 15909.

9. "Inorganic Synthesis", pp. 71-72.

TABLE I

Esters of thiophosphoric acid; O:O-Diethyl-O-aryl thiophosphates.

Aryl.	B.P./M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-Ph	110°/0.4mm	11.9	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ FPS	45.18	45.45	5.05	5.30
<i>o</i> - "	120°/0.5	17.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ FPS	45.24	45.45	5.13	5.30
4,6-Dibromo-2-fluoro-Ph	105°/2.0	14.3	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂ FPS	28.16	28.43	2.58	2.84
2,6-Dibromo-4-fluoro-Ph	110°/1.0	13.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂ FPS	28.21	28.43	2.64	2.84
2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluoro-Ph	125°/3.0	28.2	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ FI ₂ PS	23.04	23.25	2.08	2.32
2-Acetyl-4-fluoro-Ph	135°	54.4	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ FPS	46.80	47.05	5.02	5.22
2-Propionyl-4-fluoro-Ph	115°	62.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ FPS	48.48	48.75	5.62	5.34

Ph—phenyl.

Phosphoric Acid Esters.—A mixture of the appropriate phenol (1 *M*), phosphorus oxychloride (3 *M*), and Mg turnings (0.1g.) was heated at 150° for 4 hours and cooled. When distilled under reduced pressure, a liquid collected in the receiver. This distillate was heated with water for an hour and the separated product taken into ether, from which the mono-ester was isolated as usual.

The residue in the distilling flask was heated with 2*N*-NaOH solution for 6 to 8 hours. A turbid solution was obtained. It was filtered. The filtrate on acidification with HCl gave an oil, which after extraction with ether was isolated as usual. This was the di-ester.

The turbidity in the sodium hydroxide solution is attributed to the formation of the tri-ester in negligible quantity³.

To prepare the tri-esters of phosphoric acid, *i. e.*, the compounds of the type (RO)₃PO, two well-known reactions, *viz.*, using magnesium chloride or phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine, were carried out where the reactions were found to stop at the di-ester stage, indicating thereby the incapability of the phosphorus to accept the third aryl radical. The compounds prepared are listed in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

Mono-esters of phosphoric acid.

Aryl dihydrogen phosphates.	B.P./M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-Ph	110°/0.1mm.	48.6	C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ FP	37.33	37.50	3.38	3.12
<i>o</i> - "	Undistillable	85.7	C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ FP	37.39	37.50	3.34	3.12
4,6-Dibromo-2-fluoro-Ph	Do	45.0	C ₆ H ₄ O ₄ Br ₂ FP	20.34	20.57	1.03	1.04
2,6-Dibromo-4-fluoro-Ph	55°	38.4	C ₆ H ₄ O ₄ Br ₂ FP	20.42	20.57	1.01	1.04
2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluoro-Ph	35°	4.0	C ₆ H ₄ O ₄ FI ₂ P	16.01	16.21	0.75	0.90
2-Acetyl-4-fluoro-Ph	Decomposes	50.0	C ₈ H ₈ O ₅ FP	41.24	41.02	3.21	3.41
2-Propionyl-4-fluoro-Ph	Do	80.9	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₅ FP	43.30	43.54	3.82	4.03

1-Hydroxy-2-(substituted-phenoxy)-ethanes.—An equimolecular mixture of the dry sodium salt of the phenol and ethylene chlorohydrin was heated for 2 hours in dry benzene. After cooling, the benzene was distilled and the residue treated with water, when an oil separated. It was taken in ether, the ethereal layer washed with water, dried, the ether removed, and the compound distilled under reduced pressure. The compounds obtained thus are listed in Table IV. The insecticidal activity of all these compounds is under investigation.

TABLE III
Di-esters of phosphoric acid.

*Aryl hydrogen phosphate. Aryl.	BP./M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%C a r b o n.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Fluo-Ph	Undistillable; decomposes	39.0	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₄ F ₂ P	50.16	50.34	3.02	3.14
<i>o</i> - "	Do	20.0	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₄ F ₂ P	50.22	50.34	3.03	3.14
4,6-Dibromo-2-fluoroPh	Decomposes	32.0	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₄ Br ₂ F ₂ P	23.06	23.92	0.67	0.83
2,6-Dibromo-4-fluoro-Ph	165°	81.9	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₄ Br ₂ F ₂ P	23.68	23.92	0.69	0.83
2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluoro-Ph	Undistillable	42.0	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₄ F ₂ I ₂ P	18.40	18.22	0.50	0.63
2-Acetyl-4-fluoro-Ph	Decomposes	33.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆ F ₂ P	52.03	51.89	3.26	3.51
2-Propionyl-4-fluoro-Ph	Do	67.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₆ F ₂ P	54.00	54.27	4.16	4.27

TABLE IV
1-Hydroxy-2-(substituted-phenoxy)-ethanes.

Substituted-phenoxy.	B.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%C a r b o n.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
<i>p</i> -Fluoro-P	120°/0.7mm	73.4	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ F	61.38	61.53	5.61	5.76
<i>o</i> - "	120-25°/5-6	34.3	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ F	61.21	61.53	5.58	5.76
4,6-Dibromo-2-fluoro-P	155-60°/0.3-0.5	55.7	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ Br ₂ F	30.36	30.57	2.08	2.24
2,6-Dibromo-4-fluoro-P	160-70°/c.5-1.0	50.0	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ Br ₂ F	30.27	30.57	2.05	2.24
2,6-Di-iodo-4-fluoro-P	Undistillable	21.0	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ FI ₂	29.19	23.52	1.46	1.71
2-Acetyl-4-fluoro-P	105-10°/9.5	30.7	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ F	60.21	60.00	5.38	5.55
2-Propionyl-4-fluoro-P	05-100°/0.2	44.5	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ F	62.00	62.26	6.13	6.00

P=Phenoxy.

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